

SmartEdge: Semantic Low-code Programming Tools for Edge Intelligence

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Abstract

The SmartEdge project focuses on solutions to enable the low-code programmability of Edge devices and the development of applications for autonomous intelligent swarms. The project addresses three main areas, including tools for continuous semantic integration, dynamic swarm networking, and a low-code toolchain for Edge intelligence. SmartEdge utilises Semantic Web technologies to support the low-code definitions of swarm applications, enhance interoperability in the discovery and configuration of devices, and enable mediated data exchanges at runtime. The SmartEdge tools are designed, implemented and validated focusing on heterogeneous requirements from four application areas: automotive, city, factory, and health.

Keywords

Edge Intelligence, Semantic Integration, Low-code Programming

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: SmartEdge
- Project full name: Semantic Low-code Programming Tools for Edge Intelligence
- Project website link: <https://www.smart-edge.eu/>
- Start date: 01/01/2023
- End date: 31/12/2025
- Project status: Ongoing project / Ending project
- Funding agency: European Commission
- Funding programme: Horizon RIA Research and Innovation Programme
- Call identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-03
- Project partners: <https://www.smart-edge.eu/consortium/>
- Project recognition: European Commission's Innovation Radar
- Project logo: [link](#)
- Project videos: [link](#)

2. Project summary

The SmartEdge project aims to integrate decentralized edge intelligence through a semantic-based and low-code approach, facilitating autonomous intelligence swarms across edge devices. Key components include: (i) Continuous Semantic Integration (CSI) – Standardized semantic interface for device interaction and app orchestration, (ii) Dynamic Swarm Network (DSW) – Automatic discovery and formation of network swarms with embedded security, and (iii) Low-code Toolchain for Edge Intelligence –

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Semantic-driven toolkit with several extensions, designed to enable the creation of Low-Code Edge intelligence apps.

CSI in SmartEdge introduces the concept of semantic *recipes* for specifying, developing, and deploying low-code applications, promoting interoperability and reusability. A dedicated Knowledge Graph Repository is made available to support the management and discovery of devices that adhere to well-known standards like W3C Web of Things [1] and OPC UA [2]. Structured and interoperable knowledge about Edge devices also enables the effective use of Large Language Models to implement new low-code paradigms and enhance the usability of the proposed solutions.

CSI further includes a DataOps toolbox to enable semantic interoperability via a modular and declarative approach to knowledge conversion between different data representations [3, 4]. The DataOps toolbox supports the implementation of semantic conversion pipelines for the interoperability of static node information and the scalable mediation of runtime data exchanges, both on the Edge and the Cloud. Finally, a low-code toolchain supports the development and execution of recipes.

SmartEdge has been demonstrated in the automotive, city, factory, and health sectors, involving the collaboration of nine industrial partners and eight research institutes. For example, in the factory domain, the SmartEdge project leverages low-code edge intelligence to enhance manufacturing flexibility, addressing the demand for individualized production. This involves reconfigurable systems and adaptable control software. SmartEdge's edge intelligence and low-code toolchain manage control software, aiming to create semantic recipes that define capabilities, skills, and workflows. These recipes enable for rapid adaptation of hardware and software to accommodate changing orders in manufacturing [5]. In the domain of healthcare, the SmartEdge semantic recipes have been used to represent capabilities of smart wearable nodes used to track movements in the context of digital rehabilitation exercises, thus simplifying the integration of sensing and activity tracing devices [6].

3. Project available results

The main results of the project are available online and collected at the following links:

- Project public deliverables: <https://www.smart-edge.eu/deliverables/>
- SmartEdge Zenodo public repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/smartedge/records>
- SmartEdge publications (conference, journal, workshop papers): <https://www.smart-edge.eu/scientific-results/>
- SmartEdge public Git repository: <https://gitlab.com/smartedge-project-eu/smartedge-public>
- SmartEdge keynotes, talks and presentations: <https://www.smart-edge.eu/scientific-results/#prez>

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

The SmartEdge project showcases how Semantic Web technologies can be used to enable the orchestration of swarm nodes in edge architectures, bridging interoperability gaps. Being the last year of the project, its presence in the ESWC networking track will provide concrete contributions regarding the implementation of continuous semantic integration solutions for Edge environments. More specifically, SmartEdge will show how swarm tasks can be specified as semantic recipes that establish the goals and capabilities needed to accomplish them. In addition, the project will demonstrate how knowledge graphs are used to match the recipes with actual characteristics of members of an Edge/IoT swarm. Furthermore, the project could discuss its developments and validation in six use cases in different domains, including smart factories, traffic, healthcare, and autonomous robots.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

The SmartEdge project will bring to ESWC participants both scientific and innovation outcomes that can be applied in other use cases and environments. More specifically, the project can bring: (i) semantic

models for representing swarm nodes and recipes for Edge nodes; (ii) methods and lessons learned regarding the orchestration of semantic swarms; (iii) reusable components to develop DataOps pipelines for semantic interoperability; (iv) software artifacts to support low-code edge development and dynamic runtime orchestration; and (v) 6 use-case implementations showcasing the different features of the SmartEdge ecosystem.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

We expect to share lessons learned with other projects on similar and orthogonal issues, which can be conducive to potential collaborations and knowledge exchange. In particular, we aim to find new use cases where the SmartEdge results could be reused and identify open challenges for which the project's results could be a first building block. We also look forward to establishing new collaborations with other projects, especially on topics related to autonomous agents empowered by knowledge graphs, Web of Things interoperability, and semantic swarm models.

Acknowledgments

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